

Absorptive Capacity and Innovative Behaviour: Evidence From Russian Manufacturing Firms

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Abstract: The study aims to determine the connection between absorptive capacity and innovative behaviour. We analyzed firms' innovation processes and revealed the connection with their absorptive capacity at a regional level. The innovation process decomposition into sub-processes for the analysis of regional innovation processes was used in the study. For that aim, three types of innovation products were specified depending on their market and technological novelty level. Each of the types of innovation product bears the result of some innovation process implementation. For the analysis of the connection between companies' innovation process and absorptive capacity, two types of realized absorptive capacity to technological adoption from abroad will be highlighted. That adoption can take place either in disembodied or in embodied forms. The analysis uncovers that it is possible to reach large-scale innovative products with high market and technological novelty when firms intensively invest in R&D and participate in global technologies transfer, primarily in disembodied forms. The firms' ability of international technological knowledge absorption is the key factor to the innovation process. This is because most industries in these countries do not reach the level of technology of countries on the stage based on their innovations. Furthermore, the processes of innovation creation based on in-house R&D, which are performed by the firms studied, do not provide any significant contribution to the innovation process structure of the considered regions. If the regional industry's development level is relatively high but lags behind the international technological level, the scaled innovation creation processes are based on the firms' capability of the imported technologies adoption. If the companies' absorptive capacity is not large enough to transfer technological knowledge from abroad, the strategies of modifying and imitating new-to-firm products prevail in the market.

Keywords: phrases: innovation, innovation process, absorptive capacity, innovation behaviour, Russia

1. Introduction

These days the technological development of a country practically determines the competitiveness of its national economy. Along with the accelerating rates of scientific and technological progress, the technological gap between countries is increasing. As a result, advanced economies and emerging countries develop national strategies for science, technology, and innovation. As strategic priorities, the world's significant economies consider the achievement of sustainable growth, stimulation of productivity, creation of lead markets, taking the head positions in new markets, improvement of the business environment, creation of advanced technologies, enhancing of links between the participants of the innovation process (e.g. The EU Research and Innovation Programme 2021-27; The High-Tech Strategy 2025, Germany; the National Roadmap for Research, Development and Innovation, Finland). The productivity growth of these countries results from the technology gap and absorptive capacity (Dowrick, 2003). Also, these countries' companies' innovation activity bases on the processes of partnership and cooperation where the absorptive capacity plays an important role.

The strategies of catching-up and developing countries often contain not less ambitious goals. However, their overriding priority is the transition to the economy based on innovations (China The Medium- and Long-term Plan, 2012-2030; The Strategy for Innovative Development of the Russian Federation, 2035). To a large extent, these strategies are founded on catching and absorption of advanced technologies.

Therefore, research aimed at scrutinizing the absorptive capacity (Cohen and Levinthal, 1990) and firms' innovative behavior is relevant for both developed and developing countries. Many papers analyze how firms in developing countries can take advantage of technology transfer and knowledge diffusion to enhance technological development (Polterovich, Tonis, 2005; Hajek, Stejskal, 2018; Khan et al., 2019; Howell, 2020; Prokop et al., 2021).

The scientific literature covers many aspects of the relationship between absorptive capacity and innovation, including the impact of this capacity on innovative behavior (see e.g. Abreu et al., 2008; Kang and Lee, 2017; Ramayah et al., 2020). The studies emphasize the role of networks and heterogeneous sources of knowledge. For example, according to (Freund et al., 2020), an important source of foreign market and technical knowledge is weak network connections in the host country. Santoro and co-authors found a significant positive effect of firm knowledge base heterogeneity on innovation activity, but little effect of absorptive capacity (Santoro et al., 2020). Researchers often focus on R&D analysis because the positive impact of R&D on innovation has already been proven. However, “despite the extensive academic attention devoted to absorptive capacity, there are no deeper insights to date into how non-R&D firms manage the absorption of external knowledge” (Weidner, 2020). Besides, there are other types of knowledge serving as a source of innovations (Vega-Jurado et al., 2008). The purpose of our study is to find out how the absorption of significantly different types of knowledge and the innovative behavior of firms are related.

2. Literature review

Innovation activity is usually considered a consistent combination of different but connected innovation events (Landau and Rosenberg, 1986; Guan and Chen, 2011). Within this framework, innovation activity is divided into several complementary and independent stages (Bernstein and Singh, 2006). These stages are the sequence of actions from the search for knowledge resources to creating and launching new products to the market (Roper et al., 2008). In the first studies on innovation process (Utterback, 1971), innovation activity is represented as a set of primary steps, including the idea-generating, the solution to engineering problems, the innovation introduction to the market, and its diffusion. In further researches, the innovation process is considered as the linear (Clark and Fujimoto, 1991; Wheelwright and Clark, 1992; Cooper et al., 2002) or nonlinear sequence of structural phases (Cantisani, 2006; Kostas, 2006), which can overlap in time (Pavitt, 2006).

It is important to emphasize that there is no generally accepted classification of innovation stages. The allocation of innovation activity stages is typically not general and depends on the purpose of the particular study. The most widespread scheme (Hansen and Birkinshaw, 2007) is the dividing into the following three integrated stages: research and development, idea implementation, and product launch, which is accompanied by its large-scale production.

With the purpose of these complex processes implementation, companies require identifying, assimilating, and applying knowledge from the external environment. Such abilities are associated with the possibility of “absorption” of new knowledge from outside, which Cohen and Levinthal (Cohen and Levinthal, 1990) called absorptive capacity. As noted by Costa and Monteiro, based on the paper (Liao et al., 2010), “absorptive capacity mediates the relationship between knowledge sharing and innovation” (Costa and Monteiro, 2016).

Some researchers use the concept of absorptive capacity as a theoretical framework to analyze the innovation process and innovation behavior of firms (Fabrizio, 2009; Li, 2011; Costa and Monteiro, 2016; Ramayah et al., 2020). Following (Zahra and George, 2002), they often point out the difference between potential and realized absorptive capacity (Becheikh, 2013; Costa and Monteiro, 2016). The first is primarily related to the R&D efforts of companies (Cohen and Levinthal, 1990; Vega-Jurado et al., 2008; Schmidt, 2010). The number of publications, patents, and citation index scores often serve as indicators of realized absorptive capacity (George et al., 2001; Flatten et al., 2011). This type of capacity “demonstrates the ability of a firm to use consistently the integrated knowledge for commercial purposes in the long run” (Khan, et al., 2019, p.507).

Besides that, some researchers take into account the difference in the types of knowledge. Li creates a model that considers the impact of three types of investment in acquiring technological knowledge (in-house R&D, foreign technology import, and domestic technology purchase) on the firms' innovative capacity in 21 high-tech sectors (Li, 2011). Studying the behaviour of German high-tech SMEs, Freund and co-authors looked at technological and market knowledge from innovative firms, innovative suppliers, universities, and academic institutions (Freund et al., 2020). Guevara-Rocero, 2020 divided foreign knowledge according to the level of technological intensity from primary goods imports to high-tech imports.

Cassiman and Veugelers (2000) proposed a simple division of technological knowledge into embodied and disembodied forms. Embodied technology absorption implies that a firm can only absorb and use elements of the technology, and the ability to reproduce it in its entirety is quite small. In contrast, the absorption of

disembodied technology means that more knowledge is acquired and often intensive development and use of own disembodied knowledge. For example, studies (Liao et al., 2020) have shown that innovation based on the importation of disembodied technology is positively associated with industrial rationalization, while in the case of embodied technology it is depressing. Rijesh analyzed Indian manufacturing and demonstrated the positive effect of capital goods imports on engineering industries (Rijesh, 2021).

Based on these papers, we assume that different types of absorptive capacity determine the different types of firms' innovative behaviour. The critical factor of the innovation process of firms in countries at the investment stage of development is the ability of international technological knowledge absorption. This is because most industries in these countries do not reach the developed countries level of technology (see also Li, 2011).

3. Data and research method

To answer the research questions, we analyzed the innovation process of Russian companies and identified the relationship with their absorptive capacity at the regional level. The regional level was chosen for detailed analysis since regional characteristics have a significant impact on absorptive capacity and innovation activity (Abreu et al., 2008; Gokhberg and Roud, 2016). Many Russian researchers analyze innovation activity at the regional level but ignore the aspect related to the absorptive capacity of regional enterprises. This problem is considered mainly at the macro level in several papers (e.g. Polterovich and Tonis, 2005). In addition, Russian regions have a strong sectoral differentiation and are comparable to small countries in the area and population size. This allows us to operate with a sufficient amount of data. For this purpose, four regions with developed production were selected (Ayvazyan et al., 2016).

The data used in the study were provided by Russian innovation surveys dated 2009 - 2013. The firm data was collected as a random sample based on the Federal State Statistics Service database, including industrial sectors numbered 15-37 and selected service sectors numbered. The survey design is based on the Oslo Manual (OECD, 2005) and is universally accepted as compatible with the Community Innovation Survey. The database includes more than 35000 firms. The questionnaire was sent to the managers of these firms aiming to identify their innovation activities.

In the study, we use the innovation process decomposition into sub-processes to analyze regional innovation processes. For that purpose, four types of innovation products were specified depending on their level of market and technological novelty:

- 1) new-to-market and newly introduced or significantly improved innovation product;
- 2) new-to-market and only modified innovation product;
- 3) new-to-firm and newly introduced or significantly improved innovation product;
- 4) new-to-firm and only modified innovation product.

Each of the types of innovative products is the result of the implementation of one or another innovation process. The first type of product can be the result of a new product creation process or an innovation imitation process. In this case, a copy of the product is new to the local market, but already known outside it. Alternatively, the product may be produced through a combination of these processes. When R&D is a significant factor in innovation, the innovation process is likely to focus on the creation and implementation of a new product. If large-scale technology acquisition occurs, there is a high probability that an imitation innovation process has been implemented. If companies have a higher level of absorptive capacity to embrace technology in disembodied forms, absorptive capacity can be used as the basis for the process of creating new-to-market products.

Products of the second type are not considered in the study, since the cases of introduction of products new to the market and only modified products are not separated in the statistics used. It is assumed that products new to the firm and newly introduced (the third type) are the result of the process of imitation of products that are already known in local markets. It should be noted that imitation processes can be accompanied by processes of product modification and improvement using the firms' resources. Imports of embodied technologies can be used to implement these processes. The introduction of products new to the firm and previously introduced (the fourth type) means the modification of the product, which does not affect the market and technological novelty.

As characteristics of innovative products, the volume of shipped innovative products of manufacturing enterprises in Russian regions was used. Additionally, the degree of market and technological novelty was taken into account.

According to (Cassiman and Veugelers, 2000), we have considered two types of realized absorptive capacity to adopt technology from abroad. As noted above, this absorption can occur in both disembodied and embodied forms. In the first case, the total number of acquired R&D results, patents and licenses, and know-how from abroad were analyzed. As characteristics of the second type of absorptive capacity, we used the number of technologies acquired when purchasing equipment.

Further, we applied a qualitative analysis comparing the absorption of foreign knowledge and the types of innovations produced. This method allowed us to consider the difference in lags between the assimilation and use of embodied and disembodied technologies and the production of goods.

4. Innovation process of Russian regional enterprise

4.1 The Nizhni Novgorod region

The majority of innovative products is manufactured by firms working in the following industries: manufacture of coke and refined petroleum products; metallurgy; automobile manufacture. In such a case, the firms engaged in the manufacturing of coke and refined petroleum products make the most significant contribution to the regional industry's sectoral structure.

In general, the innovation activity of the Nizhni Novgorod regional enterprises is significantly high. Within the studied period, there is a steady growth in the sector of innovative products. In 2010-2011 there was a quick change of the characteristics of products quality. The essential part of firms turned from the manufacturing of known in the local market innovative products to the release of new and unknown products in the trading area. It is likely possible by the intensive acquisition of technologies in embodied and disembodied forms from abroad (see Figure 1). It is noteworthy that there is a substantial growth in expenditures on the research and development of new products, services, and production methods.

Figure 1: The international technology acquisition by the Russian enterprises

This proves that the creation of new competitive advantages in the local market through the launch of new products is primarily based on the adoption and adaptation of imported technologies. To be able to adopt these technologies, companies must increase their absorptive capacity by investing in their research. Consequently, firms are shifting from innovation activities based on minor modifications of previous products to their innovative creation and imitation of products not known in the local market but already known outside it (see Figure 2). The introduction of many new innovative products in 2010 caused imitation processes by free-riders not investing in imported technologies acquisition (Rogers, 2003). Since 2011 companies adopted innovations created by other market participants that significantly increased the scale of innovation product distribution inside the region. Participation in imitation processes required the acquisition of foreign technologies in

embodied forms from enterprises. In 2012-2013 the majority of manufactured innovative products was the result of that behavioural type following. At this stage, the adoption of technologies in embodied forms was dramatically decreased, which is possible to connect to the gain of competitive advantages of the companies capable of absorbing non-domestic technologies. They accomplished the innovation cycle for a while.

Figure 2: The structure of innovation process of Nizhni Novgorod regional companies

Despite the significant increase of Nizhny Novgorod regional companies' innovative activity and product novelty, the earlier laid groundwork (2010-2011) appeared insufficient to maintain remarkable product novelty for a more extended period. In 2013 a drop in the sales of new-to-market products was observed. Besides, there is the tendency of sales decreasing of newly introduced innovative products. However, this tendency is not strong due to the products copying by the follower enterprises.

4.2 The Omsk region

Chemical industrial companies manufacture the most significant part of the regional production. The share of these firms in the innovative products constitutes 55%. It stands to mention that the share of innovative products among all industry products is relatively high and makes 28%. In the sectoral structure of the industry, the share of the chemical industry does not exceed 5%, in any case. The remarkable contributions to innovative regional products belong to firms producing electronic components, radio, television broadcasting, and communications equipment (22%), and firms engaged in rubber and plastic products (16%). The manufacture makes the prevailing contribution to the sectoral structure of the Omsk regional industry of coke and oil products. However, the innovation activity of these companies is not intense. Such a situation is not typical for all regions where this industry is developed. On average, the share of innovative products is at the level of 10% regarding this type of production.

In the studied period (2009-2013) innovation activity can be characterized by a low level of innovation diffusion. The share of innovative products in this period did not exceed 6%. At the same time, a significant part of these products was new to the market and recently introduced. Most likely, it is connected with the accelerated introduction of innovations new for the market in separate branches against the background of low intensity of creation and imitation of innovations by enterprises of other branches. In other words, only a small part of regional firms had the necessary level of competence to introduce new products, including absorptive capacity. However, thanks to the activities of these companies, the prevailing processes of imitation of products that were already known on the local market were replaced in 2010 by the predominance of innovation creation (see Figure 3). Since 2011, the processes of modification of previous innovations have again become significant. However, firms were intensely involved in the processes of creating and imitating innovations. Those firms that moved from innovation to subsequent modification had all but exhausted their opportunities to gain competitive advantage by 2013. For this reason, some of them acquired new international technologies in a disembodied form in 2013 to make the transition to new products or new innovation cycles, to put it differently.

Figure 3: The structure of innovation process of Omsk regional companies

4.3 The Vladimir region

The regional innovation activity is concentrated in machinery and equipment production, although the regional sectoral structure of the industry is diverse. Companies engaged in the manufacture of machinery and equipment and firms producing medical goods provide the most outstanding contribution (on 17.9% in 2012) to the regional innovation production. In such a case, the share of the former in all regional products constitutes 10,2%, and the share of the latter is only 4%. Besides, the characteristics of product novelty are also different in these industries. The share of new-to-market innovative products is at the level of 97% for machinery and equipment production. In the instant case, the basis of innovation activity is the acquisition of embodied technologies. More than 96% of the expenditures on technological innovations are used for the purchase of machinery and equipment. The companies engaged in the production of medical goods acquire machinery and equipment for innovations (41% of total expenditures on technological innovations) and invest in in-house R&D (54% of total expenditures on technological innovations). The share of new-to-market innovative products does not exceed 12% for this industry, however.

In 2009-2010, the basis of innovation activity of regional firms was imitation and follow-up products already known in the local market (see Figure 4). Since 2010, there has been an increase in the novelty of the product market due to a significant increase in the cost of developing new products, as well as an increase in investment in the acquisition of new technologies. However, firms only acquired non-domestic technologies in embodied forms. Since the region showed the lowest innovation activity between 2003 and 2009 (Shepina, 2012), it can be assumed that firms do not have sufficient absorptive capacity to diffuse higher-level technologies.

In 2013 a slight decrease in costs on R&D and a drop in expenditures on technology acquisition was observed. The characteristics of product quality were increasing, however. The available absorptive capacity allowed companies to adopt acquired technologies from abroad and to reach more than tenfold growth of the scale of new-to-market innovation product distribution within the studied period. Unlike the Nizhni Novgorod region enterprises, the companies of the studied area were able to imply imitation purely and modifying processes. Thus, the quality of produced innovative goods is lower in this region.

Figure 4: The structure of innovation process of Vladimir regional companies

The essential role of technological import in the innovation processes is proved true by the significant ratio of costs on imported technologies to the value of both total production and its innovative component. This fact also confirms the assumption that the growth in innovation activity is in many respects connected with innovation imitation of products that are new to the local markets but already known outside.

4.4 The Vologda Region

The innovation activity of the region concentrates on the metallurgical industry, which also makes the most significant contribution to the sectoral structure of the industry (71% and 59% correspondently). The second place in product sales belongs to chemical industrial firms (10%), the enterprises engaged in electrical power distribution and transmission (7%), and food production companies (7%) follow further.

For the metal manufacturer, the diffusion scale and characteristics of innovation products novelty are on low levels. The share of innovative products does not exceed 6%, from which 94% of products are already known to the market. Companies maintain the innovation status of the products through insignificant modification, which changes neither market nor technological products novelty. It is to note that firms do not aim to purchase technology in embodied or disembodied forms. It also stands to mention that not all Russian metals companies show the low novelty of innovative products. It is possible to consider the Volgograd, Kirov, and Chelyabinsk regions companies as examples.

In general, the quality of the innovation process in the Vologda region is relatively low. The basis of the regional innovation activity is using external knowledge. In addition, the technologies used are neither innovative nor even new for the local market. In 2009 - 2011 the processes of modification and imitation of previously introduced innovations dominated. Poor product quality prevented companies from achieving widespread adoption of innovations. During this period there was an increase in expenditures on the acquisition of Russian technologies. This allowed companies to increase the level of diffusion of innovations in the market in 2012-2013. The scale of diffusion, in any case, remained low compared to the average Russian level. The insufficient level of financial and absorption capabilities of firms did not allow them to participate either in the creation of innovations or in imitation processes when introducing foreign technologies (see Figure 5). Thus, it was not possible to significantly increase the scale of innovation diffusion and, in general, to improve the quality of the innovation process.

Figure 5: The structure of innovation process of Vologda regional companies

5. Results and limitations

The analysis shows the possibility of achieving large-scale diffusion of innovative products with high market and technological novelty when firms intensively invest in R&D and participate in global technology transfer, mostly in disembodied forms. The patterns found are generally consistent with Liao et al., 2020. Moreover, the processes of innovation creation based on internal R&D carried out by various firms do not contribute significantly to the structure of innovation processes of the regions under consideration. For example, in the Nizhny Novgorod region after 2012 innovative companies could not keep the novelty of the market and technological products without accelerated non-embodied technology transfer, despite the growth of R&D costs and embodied acquisition of foreign technologies. The latter turns out to be sufficient only for the growth of innovation diffusion. This is demonstrated by the Vladimir region. Thus, the positive effect of imports of embodied technologies (Ridgesh, 2021) on the economy of the region is not so significant. In addition, there is a danger of firms falling into the trap of imitation.

Acquisition of international technology in disembodied form means launching a new innovation cycle with a high probability. In this case, firms that have exhausted their previous competitive advantages begin to acquire such technologies to create a new product. Some imports "with more technological intensity" (Guevara-Rosero, 2020) allow to form such local advantages. In particular, the results of the analysis of the Omsk region confirm this hypothesis.

The basis of the innovative activity of the Vologda region is innovative products copied earlier from others. During the studied period the companies did not purchase foreign technologies and did not invest in their own R&D. As a result, products with the lowest level of novelty, i.e. known to the market and of low quality, appeared in their production. Large-scale distribution in this case is impossible.

The study covers several regions, and their heterogeneity is mainly due to industry differences. However, we do not consider the heterogeneity of firms (e.g., Howell, 2020) or knowledge sources (e.g., Santoro et al., 2020). It should be noted that the lack of available funding can be seen as a factor that significantly limits the growth of absorptive capacity and leads to its loss in some circumstances. Researchers also highlight determinants of absorptive capacity and innovation such as foreign investment, labor flow, and digitalization (e.g., Girma, 2005; Kang and Lee, 2017; Khan et al., 2019; Calvino et al., 2020). Therefore, future studies may elaborate on these aspects. Our results can be considered preparatory for quantitative analysis. At the same time, this study helps to identify the lag and detail the qualitative effects of embodied and unembodied technology adoption on innovation behavior.

6. Conclusions

Overall, our results confirm that if the level of regional industry development is relatively high but lags behind the international technological level, large-scale innovation creation processes are based on the ability of firms to adopt imported technologies (Li, 2011; Howell, 2020; Ramayah et al., 2020). We found that firms' new product

modification and imitation strategies prevail in the market of selected regions if the absorptive capacity of firms is not large enough to transfer technological knowledge from abroad. Moreover, the presence of absorptive capacity to adopt disembodied technologies is a motivation to start a new innovation cycle aimed at gaining a competitive advantage from the launch of a new product. Thus, the prevailing innovative behavior and the structure of the innovation process depend on the ability of firms to absorb different types of knowledge.

Regions with economic advantages can benefit most from importing technology (Guevara-Rosero, 2020). By developing and combining the firms' absorptive capacity of different knowledge types, regions also benefit more. In other words, absorptive capacity is a factor of regional inequality. The pandemic and the crisis further emphasize the need to increase absorptive capacity to reduce these inequalities and barriers to knowledge transfer.

References

- Abreu, M., Grinevich, V., Kitson, M., Savona, M. (2008) "Absorptive Capacity and Regional Patterns of Innovation". In Research Report 8/11 (London: Department of Innovation, Universities, and Skills).
- Aivizian, S.A., Afanasiev, M. Yu., Kudrov, A. V. (2016) "Models of Productive Capacity and Technological Efficiency Evaluations of Regions of the Russian Federation Concerning the Output Structure", *Economics and Mathematical Methods* 52(1), pp. 28-44.
- Becheikh, N. (2013). "The Impact of Knowledge Acquisition and Absorptive Capacity on Technological Innovations in Developing Countries: Evidence From Egyptian Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises", *Journal of African Business*. 14(3), pp.127-140.
- Bernstein, B., Singh, P.J. (2006) "An integrated innovation process model based on practices of Australian biotechnology firms", *Technovation* 26, pp. 561–572.
- Cantisani, A. (2006) "Technological innovation process revisited", *Technovation* 26(11), pp. 1294-1301.
- Cassiman, B. and R. Veugelers (2000), 'External technology sources: Embodied or disembodied technology acquisition', University Pompeu Fabra, Economics and Business WP 444.
- Clark, K.B., Fujimoto, T. (1991) *Product Development Performance: Strategy, Organisation and Management in the World Auto Industry*, Harvard Business School Press, Boston.
- Calvino, F., Criscuolo and R. Verlhac (2020), "Declining business dynamism: Structural and policy determinants", *OECD Science, Technology and Industry Policy Papers*, No. 94, OECD Publishing, Paris.
- Cohen, W.M., Levinthal, D.A. (1990) "Absorptive-capacity—a new perspective on learning and innovation", *Administrative Science Quarterly* 35 (1), pp. 128–152.
- Cooper, R.G., Edgett, S.J., Kleinschmidt, E.J. (2002) "Optimizing the stage-gate process: what best practice companies do", *Research-Technology Management* 45 (5), pp. 21–27.
- Costa, V., Monteiro, S. (2016) "Knowledge Processes, Absorptive Capacity and Innovation: A Mediation Analysis", *Knowledge and Process Management* 23(3), pp. 207–218.
- Dowrick S. (2003), *A Review of the Evidence on Science, R&D and Productivity*, Working Paper, Department of Education, Science and Training, The Australian National University.
- Fabrizio, K. (2009) "Absorptive Capacity and the Search for Innovation", *Research Policy* 38(2), pp. 255–267.
- Flatten, T. C., Engelen, A., Shaker A. Zahra, M. B. (2011) "A measure of absorptive capacity: Scale development and validation", *European Management Journal* 29 (2), pp. 98-116.
- Freund, D., Lee, R., Tüselmann, H., & Cao, Q. (2020). International high-tech SMEs innovative foreign knowledge inflows: effects of host country weak network ties and absorptive capacity. *Multinational Business Review*.
- George, G., Zahra, S., Wheatley, K., Khan, R. (2001) "The effects of alliance portfolio characteristics and absorptive capacity on performance: A study of biotechnology firms", *Journal of High Technology Management Research* 12, pp. 205–226.
- Girma, S. (2005). Absorptive capacity and productivity spillovers from FDI: a threshold regression analysis. *Oxford bulletin of Economics and Statistics*, 67(3), 281-306.
- Gokhberg, L., Roud, V. (2016) "Structural changes in the national innovation system: longitudinal study of innovation modes in the Russian industry", *Economics change and restructuring* 49, pp. 269-288.
- Guan, J., Chen, K. (2011) "Mapping the innovation production process from accumulate advantage to economic outcomes: a path modeling approach", *Technovation* 31, pp. 336-346.
- Guevara-Rosero, G. C. (2020). "Trade, innovation and agglomeration. A case study for Colombia". *Estudios Gerenciales*, 36(155), pp. 156-166.
- Hajek P, Stejskal J. (2018) *Intelligent Prediction of Firm Innovation Activity—The Case of Czech Smart Cities*. In: *Information Innovation Technology in Smart Cities*. Singapore: Springer. pp. 123–136.
- Hansen, M.T., Birkinshaw, J. (2007). "The innovation value chain", *Harvard Business Review* 85 (July), pp. 121-130.
- Howell, A. (2020). "Relatedness economies, absorptive capacity, and economic catch-up: firm-level evidence from China". *Industrial and Corporate Change*, 29(2), pp. 557-575.

- Justin, J.P. Jansen Frans, A.J. Van Den Bosch Henk, W. Volberda (2003) "Absorptive Capacity, Adaptation, And Performance: An Intra-Organizational Perspective", [online], www2.warwick.ac.uk/fac/soc/wbs/conf/olkc/archive/olkc4/papers/olkc2003_jansen.pdf
- Kang, M., and M.J. Lee (2017) "Absorptive Capacity, Knowledge Sharing, and Innovative Behaviour of R&D Employees." *Technology Analysis & Strategic Management* 29 (2), pp. 219–232.
- Khan, Z., Lew, Y. K., & Marinova, S. (2019). "Exploitative and exploratory innovations in emerging economies: The role of realized absorptive capacity and learning intent". *International Business Review*, 28(3), 499-512.
- Kostas, G. (2006) "Innovation process. Make sense using systems thinking", *Technovation* 26(11), pp. 1222-1232.
- Landau, R., Rosenberg, N. (Eds.). (1986) *The positive sum strategy: Harnessing technology for economic growth*, National Academies Press.
- Liao, H., Yang, L., Ma, H., & Zheng, J. (2020). Technology import, secondary innovation, and industrial structure optimization: A potential innovation strategy for China. *Pacific Economic Review*, 25(2), 145-160.
- Li, X. (2011) "Sources of External Technology, Absorptive Capacity, and Innovation Capability in Chinese State-Owned High-Tech Enterprises", *World Development* 39(7), pp. 1240–1248.
- Liao, S., Wu, C., Hu, C, Tsui, A. (2010). "Relationships between knowledge acquisition, absorptive capacity and innovation capability: an empirical study on Taiwan's financial and manufacturing industries", *Journal of Information Science* 36(1), pp. 19–35.
- Pavitt, K. (2006) *Innovation Processes*, in *The Oxford Handbook of Innovation* eds. R. R. Nelson, D. C. Mowery and J. Fagerberg, Oxford University Press, Oxford.
- Polterovich, V., Tonis A. (2005): *Innovation and Imitation at Various Stages of Development: A Model with Capital*. Working paper #2005/048. M.: New Economic School.
- Prokop V., Stejskal J., Klimova V., Zitek V. (2021). The role of foreign technologies and R&D in innovation processes within catching-up CEE countries. *PLoS ONE* 16(4): e0250307.
- Ramayah, T., Soto-Acosta, P., Kheng, K.K. and Mahmud, I. (2020), "Developing process and product innovation through internal and external knowledge sources in manufacturing Malaysian firms: the role of absorptive capacity", *Business Process Management Journal*, Vol. 26 No. 5, pp. 1021-1039.
- Rijesh, R. (2021). "Liberalization, Import of Capital Goods, and Industrial Exports: Evidence from Indian Manufacturing Sectors". *Global Journal of Emerging Market Economies* 13(1), pp. 81-103.
- Rogers, E. M. (2003) *Diffusion of Innovations*, 5th Edition. N.Y.: Free Press.
- Roper, S., Dub, J., Loveb, J.H. (2008) "Modeling the innovation value chain", *Research Policy* 37(6-7), pp. 961-977.
- Santoro, G., Bresciani, S., & Papa, A. (2020). "Collaborative modes with cultural and creative industries and innovation performance: the moderating role of heterogeneous sources of knowledge and absorptive capacity". *Technovation*, 92, 102040.
- Schmidt, T. (2010) "Absorptive Capacity: One Size Fits All? a Firm-Level Analysis of Absorptive Capacity for Different Kinds of Knowledge", *Managerial and Decision Economics* 31, pp. 1-18.
- Shchepina, I.N. (2012) *Innovazionnaya deyatel'nost' na regional'nom urovne: tipy povedeniya regionov i ih ustoychivost'*, Voronezh
- Utterback, J.M. (1971) "The process of technological innovation within the firm", *The Academy of Management Journal* 14 (1), pp. 75–88.
- Vega-Jurado, J., Gutierrez-Gracia, A., Fernandez-De-Lucio, I. (2008) "Analyzing the Determinants of Firm's Absorptive Capacity: Beyond R&D", *R&D Management* 38 (4), pp. 392-405.
- Weidner, N. (2020). Paper to be presented at the DRUID Academy Conference 2020 at University of Southern Denmark, Odense, Denmark January 16-17, 2020. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 35(1), 128-152.
- Wheelwright, S.C., Clark, K.B. (1992) *Revolutionizing Product Development: Quantum Leaps in Speed, Efficiency and Quality*, Free Press, New York.
- Zahra, S.A., George, G. (2002) "Absorptive capacity: a review, reconceptualization, and extension", *Academy of Management Review* 27(2), pp.185–203.